

Review Article

Monstrous Women or Victims of Patriarchy? A Theoretical Exploration of Female Monstrosity in *My Sister, the Serial Killer* and *Woman at Point Zero*

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OPEN ACCESS**Abstract**

This study explores the concept of female monstrosity in Oyinkan Braithwaite's *My Sister, the Serial Killer* and Nawal El Saadawi's *Woman at Point Zero*, examining how societal structures shape women into perceived monsters. Using Julia Kristeva's Abjection Theory and Jeffrey Jerome Cohen's Monster Culture Theory, the research investigates whether these female protagonists are inherently monstrous or products of patriarchal oppression. Kristeva's theory posits that the abject, what is expelled from the self, disrupts identity and order, making women who defy societal norms appear monstrous. Cohen, on the other hand, argues that monsters are cultural constructs reflecting societal fears and anxieties. In *My Sister, the Serial Killer*, Ayoola and Korede's monstrosity stems from childhood trauma inflicted by their abusive father. Ayoola's impulsive killings and Korede's complicity highlight how violence breeds monstrosity in different ways. Similarly, *Woman at Point Zero* portrays Firdaus as a victim of systemic oppression who ultimately reclaims agency through murder, an act that society labels monstrous. Both novels demonstrate that female monstrosity is not an innate condition but a response to patriarchal violence and repression. By applying Kristeva's and Cohen's frameworks, this study reveals that monstrosity is both a reaction to oppression and a reflection of societal failings. The findings suggest that women labelled as monsters are often shaped by their circumstances rather than an inherent evil. Finally, this research challenges traditional perceptions of female monstrosity, urging a reconsideration of how gender, trauma, and power intersect in literature and society.

Key words: Female Monstrosity, Abjection, Patriarchy, Trauma, Monster Theory**Introduction**

In every human society, concepts of good and bad coexist, often falling within the realm of normalcy and acceptability. However, when actions or behaviours transcend into the extraordinarily bad or abnormal, they evoke a sense of monstrosity. Traditionally, the term "monstrous" conjures images of mythical creatures like giants, zombies, vampires, werewolves, and dragons - figments of human imagination. [1], observed, "monstrosity is not a physical thing; it is a question of social otherness, of the corruption of an individual's interaction with society" [23]. She further poses, "if a tree falls in a forest and no one is around to hear it, does it make a sound? If a monster is lurking and there is no one to be threatened by it, is it a monster?" [23]. This suggests that the concept of monstrosity is defined by societal perceptions and the presence of an observer. [2], also observed that monsters "get defined in relation to communities and to their standards of what is good, acceptable, normal or natural... . In different times, places and cultures, or from different viewpoints within a single culture, different answers will emerge" (x). Bremmer cited in [3], supported the view that, "... to a large extent monsters are culturally determined. Each culture has its own preoccupations and fears, its own definitions of 'normal', its own manner of looking at reality" [104]. Therefore, it is obvious now that cultures create monsters and imbue them with meaning, shaping their traits from their most entrenched fears and taboos. The monster's body serves as a canvas for these cultural anxieties, manifesting what society forbids. It does not simply reflect fear, desire, and uncertainty, it embodies them, granting them an unsettling vitality. A monster refuses to be contained,

breaking free from its creator's control, exceeding its limits, and ultimately turning against those who brought it into existence.

Monstrosity often serves as a mirror reflecting societal fears and prejudices. [4], discussed how, before scientific advancements, deformed humans, such as conjoined twins, were labeled as monsters, eliciting reactions ranging from horror to repugnance. [5], posited that monsters are human constructs reflecting their creators, serving as mirrors for humanity. To support the above, [3], suggested that ... "monsters tend to reflect various cultural anxieties; different monsters across various time periods and a multitude of settings - whether ancient or modern - can represent multifaceted and shifting societal concerns. But taken all together, the monsters of myth, legend, and folktale function to reflect our fears and hopes about the mysteries of the natural world... [130]" This shows that monstrosity cannot exist outside human perception. Thus, monsters are not solely mythical creatures but also individuals whose behaviours deviate from societal norms. In further explaining that, Cohen reiterated that:

while much of what was monstrous to people hundred of years ago might be merely mundane to us today, the concept remains the same. A monster is not merely a specific class of mythical being or a descriptive label for that which incites fear; rather, it is an embodiment of cultural meaning that invites us to look beyond the physical realm into the psychological, requesting that we question not just what classifies as a monster, but why those beings are monstrous [4].

[6], nonetheless, is not the only scholar with this view, [7] also said, “all cultures create their own monsters” [5]. Goetsch noted: “there are no monsters in reality; instead, monsters are cultural constructs that invite both interpretation and criticism” [5]. Historical atrocities, such as the Holocaust orchestrated by Hitler, the attempted rape of Miranda by Caliban in Shakespeare’s [8]. *The Tempest*, and contemporary crimes like organ harvesting, exemplify human monstrosity.

Historically, humans have labeled unfamiliar or abnormal beings as monsters, often driven by a desire to assert superiority over the “other.” This dehumanization facilitates a lack of empathy, making it easier to justify cruel actions against those deemed monstrous. [6], asserted that depicting another culture as monstrous justifies its displacement or extermination by rendering the act heroic. For example, labeling black individuals as “savage” or “barbaric” has historically been used to rationalize their oppression. Similarly, women who defy patriarchal norms have been branded as “mad,” with Cohen noting that such women risk becoming figures like Scylla or Lilith. In literature, characters like Bertha Mason in Charlotte Brontë’s *Jane Eyre* are portrayed as mad, obscuring the actions of those who may have contributed to their plight. This type of monster, the “monstrous-feminine” or female monster is only but a reflection of the patriarchal society’s fear of women being measured as equal to the men and not essentially that the women are monstrous in the real sense of it.

This study therefore, investigates the motivations behind women’s actions labeled as monstrous, questioning whether these behaviours are inherently evil or responses to societal constructs. By analyzing Oyinkan Braithwaite’s [9]. *My Sister, The Serial Killer* and Nawal El Saadawi’s [10]. *Woman at Point Zero*, the research explores how patriarchal oppression and psychological factors influence such behaviours. In Braithwaite’s novel, the protagonist’s violent tendencies are examined through the lens of familial abuse and societal pressures. Similarly, El Saadawi’s work examines how patriarchal oppression and sexual violence can lead to traumatic responses and extreme actions. These analyses aim to provide a nuanced understanding of the factors influencing women’s engagement in behaviours labeled as monstrous.

Female Monstrosity in Literature, Gaming, and Society

Scholars have long debated the portrayal of female monstrosity in literature, gaming, and cultural narratives. [11], argued that the representation of female bodies as monstrous is a tool of patriarchal control. They examine the game’s Ludic Bestiary, which classifies female figures such as the “hag” as abject and evil, reinforcing misogynistic stereotypes across other digital games. [12], expanded on this where she critiques how video games depict female monsters as obstacles that a male hero must slay to restore patriarchal order. This, she argues, normalizes gender-based violence in popular culture. [13], further explored these themes in “Shrieking, Biting, and Licking: The Monstrous-Feminine” in Video Games, highlighting how games like “*The Witcher* and *God of War*” represent female monsters as grotesque beings that attack male protagonists through biting, licking, or spreading disease. These portrayals align with horror media’s long tradition of depicting women’s bodies as threatening.

A similar patriarchal pattern exists in literature. [14], examined how 19th-century English domestic fiction constructs female monstrosity within a rigid socio-political framework. Drawing from Kristeva’s abjection theory, she reveals how cultural anxieties shape narratives that vilify women who disrupt patriarchal norms. [15], argued that patriarchal control transforms women into symbols of national anxiety. He critiques Singapore’s phallogocentric ideology [155], which blames women for social issues such as declining birth rates, reinforcing their role as scapegoats. Through films like “*Return to Pontianak* and *The Maid*”, [15], showed how female monstrosity serves as a ritualistic means of patriarchal discipline.

This phenomenon extends to professional spaces and that is why [16], argued that female lawyers who defy patriarchal expectations are depicted as mentally unstable or monstrous. Their analysis of *Laws of Attraction*, Michael Clayton, and *I Am Sam* demonstrates how ambition and defiance in women are equated with monstrosity. [17], also highlighted how racial and gender biases construct women of colour as monstrous within academia. By aligning her experiences with literary depictions of shape-shifters and werewolves, she critiques systemic oppression and advocates for greater inclusivity.

[18], examined how female antagonists are historically portrayed as monsters. She analyzes Lewis’s *Narnia* series, Dahl’s *The Witches*, and Pullman’s *The Amber Spyglass*, using Kristeva’s Abjection Theory and Barbara Creed’s concept of the Monstrous-Feminine. Bo Tso argued that in *Narnia* and *The Witches*, female villains are portrayed as the abject that corrodes the borderlines between life and death, human and non-human, masculine and feminine, after which the stories end with the ejection of the monstrous-feminine in order to restore a supposed assumed normality in the order of things. Even in *The Amber Spyglass*, where monstrous-feminine characters gain some autonomy, they still remain secondary to the patriarchal order. This study aligns with the argument that female monstrosity is a tool used to reinforce gender norms.

[19], examined how medieval women were turned into monsters through gender ideologies. She argues that societal structures, rather than inherent evil, created female monsters, “The accepted conventions of misogyny, patriarchal authority, and the romance ‘formula itself’... are responsible for breeding medieval women into monsters” (ii). Analyzing Melusine, Chaucer’s and Gower’s *Constance* tales, and Medes’ Depictions in medieval literature, Urban highlights how patriarchal anxieties led to the portrayal of women as monstrous. She states that “Monstrous women in these stories offer their narratives as a means to interrogate the prevailing gender ideology; expose the constructedness of and agenda behind existing ideological, political, social, familial, and physical spheres” (ii). This aligns with Cohen’s [6], argument that monsters reflect societal fears rather than existing as independent entities.

Therefore, Kristeva’s and Cohen’s theories highlight how societies create monsters to enforce social norms. Women who challenge the patriarchal order, whether through independence, violence, or sexual autonomy, are labeled monstrous. [20], wrote, “Monsters are things that should not be, but nevertheless are—and their existence raises vexing questions about humanity’s understanding of and place in the universe... The monster undoes our understanding of the way things are and violates our sense of how they are supposed to be” [1-2]. Similarly, Mittman and [21], noted that, “They not only challenge and question; they trouble, they worry, they haunt. They break and tear down and rend cultures, all the while constructing them and propping them up” [20].

The existing researches emphasize how patriarchal structures demonize non-conforming women in literature, gaming, and society. However, a key question remains: Are female monsters merely victims of patriarchy, or do some actions justify their monstrosity? This study explores female monstrosity in *My Sister, the Serial Killer* and *Woman at Point Zero* through Kristeva’s Abjection Theory and Cohen’s Monster Culture Theory to determine whether these women are truly monstrous or products of societal injustice.

[22], Abjection Theory explored how individuals reject aspects of themselves to maintain a sense of order. She defines the abject as that which is rejected from the self and perceived as ‘other’ or ‘alien’ yet remains a part of the self. The abject disrupts identity and order. It is not lack of cleanliness or health that causes abjection but what disturbs identity, system, and order. What does not respect borders, positions, and rules. The in-between,

the ambiguous, the composite. Kristeva argues that society abjects what it considers impure or disruptive, including deviant individuals. She likens this to bodily fluids - vomit, feces - originally part of us but expelled to maintain social and psychological cleanliness. This expulsion is driven by the superego, which dictates societal norms, A certain 'ego' that merged with its master, a superego has flatly driven it away. To each ego its object, to each superego its abject.

The abject is also a cultural construct, shaping social hierarchies and power structures. As [22], stated, that by way of abjection, primitive societies have marked out a precise area of their culture in order to remove it from the threatening world of animals or animalism. Applied to female monstrosity, this theory suggests that patriarchal societies abject women who challenge norms. Women who refuse submission are seen as monstrous because they blur the lines of social acceptability.

[6], argued that monsters are not just fictional beings but cultural constructs reflecting societal anxieties. His Seven Theses explain the role of monsters in shaping cultural identity.

1. The Monster's Body is a Cultural Body: Monsters represent the fears, desires, and anxieties of the cultures that create them. Cohen writes, "The monster is born only at the metaphoric crossroads, as an embodiment of a certain cultural moment... The monstrous body is pure culture" [4].
2. Monsters Always Escape: They reappear in new forms throughout history, adapting to cultural fears.
3. The Monster is the Harbinger of Category Crisis: Monsters blur boundaries, defying traditional classifications, "The monster always escapes because it refuses categorization" [6].
4. The Monster Dwells at the Gates of Difference: Monsters symbolize marginalized groups, reinforcing social hierarchies.
5. The Monster Polices the Borders of the Possible: They serve as warnings against transgression.
6. Fear of the Monster is Really a Kind of Desire: Monsters attract as much as they repel, "The monster also attracts... linking of monstrosity with the forbidden makes the monster all the more appealing" [16-17].
7. The Monster Stands at the Threshold... of Becoming: Monsters force societies to confront their own assumptions, "Monsters ask us why we have created them" [20].

Using these theories, this study examines how the female protagonists in *My Sister, the Serial Killer* and *Woman at Point Zero* are labeled as monstrous. Their "monstrosity" is not inherent but a reflection of societal anxieties about female autonomy. This study, therefore, argues that the female "monsters" in *My Sister, the Serial Killer* and *Woman at Point Zero* are not inherently monstrous. Rather, they are products of human fear, constructed to reinforce societal norms and boundaries, hence the title, *Monstrous Women or Victims of Patriarchy? A Theoretical Exploration of Female Monstrosity in My Sister, the Serial Killer and Woman at Point Zero*,

Female Monsters as Products of Human and Social Constructs in Oyinkan Braithwaite's *My Sister, the Serial Killer* and Nawal El Saadawi's *Woman at Point Zero*

[6], Monster Culture theory posits that monsters are human creations, stating, "monsters are our children" [20]. This analogy implies that, like offspring resembling their parents, monsters reflect aspects of human nature and society. Similarly, the Igbo proverb, "a snake will not fail to beget what is not long," suggests that beings produce offspring in their own likeness. Julia Kristeva's Abjection theory further explored this concept by examining how certain elements are expelled from the self to maintain identity. In her work "Powers of Horror: An Essay on Abjection," Kristeva describes the abject as that which "disturbs identity, system, order" and

"does not respect borders, positions, rules." This process of abjection involves rejecting parts of ourselves that we find undesirable, thereby maintaining the boundaries of our identity. These theories collectively suggest that what we consider monstrous is often a reflection of the aspects of humanity that we reject or fail to acknowledge. [23], observed, "monsters are our mirrors; in them, we see who we hope we are not, in order to understand who we are (n.p)." This introspection leads us to question whether, like [24], 'Chichidodo' in *The Beautiful Ones Are Not Yet Born*, we deceive ourselves into believing we are detached from filth, while in reality, we consume what is born from it.

The primary objective of this analysis is to explore the origins of female monstrosity: are these women inherently monstrous from birth, or do societal influences and human actions shape their monstrous identities? In Oyinkan Braithwaite's *My Sister, the Serial Killer*, the sisters Ayoola and Korede exemplify this inquiry. While previous discussions have established their monstrous behaviours, it remains crucial to understand the catalysts behind their transformation. The Igbo proverb, "an action is what begets another action (*ihe na akpata ihe*)," emphasizes the notion that behaviours are reactions to preceding events. In societal contexts, individual actions, such as a parent's failure to properly nurture a child, can have widespread repercussions, affecting the community at large. Similarly, Ayoola and Korede's monstrous actions (mercilessly killing and harming innocent victims) did not emerge in isolation. They are products of trauma and abuse, particularly stemming from their father's actions, aligning with Cohen's assertion that monsters are created, not born.

In the novel, their father is portrayed as a ruthless individual, primarily concerned with his political ambitions and reputation, often at the expense of his family's well-being. He openly disrespects their mother, bringing his mistress into their home. When their mother confronts him, the situation escalates violently:

She never raised her voice to him. But that night, she was like a banshee; her fro was free of its bands and restraints, adding to the illusion of madness. She was Medusa, and they were statues before her. She went to wrench the woman off his arm. 'E gba mi o! So fe yi mi lori ni? Oluwa koju si mi!...I remember hissing at my mother, even though there were tears in my eyes. I remember thinking how silly she looked, so worked up as he stood tall and impassive before her...beside me, Ayoola held her breath...I understand now, too, that though my mother must have been aware of his indiscretions, having them take place in her home was more than she could bear...moments later he pulled our mother off her feet by her hair, and slammed her against the wall. Then he struck her face. Ayoola whimpered and clutched me [85].

This passage illustrates that every individual has a threshold for tolerance. When pushed beyond this limit, suppressed aspects of one's personality can surface. Korede's mother, typically submissive, reaches her breaking point when her husband's infidelity invades her home, leading to an outburst that Korede describes using terms like "banshee" and "Medusa." These descriptors suggest that latent monstrous traits exist within everyone, surfacing under extreme circumstances. Thus, the emergence of such traits in Ayoola and Korede can be seen as a response to their traumatic experiences, shaped by their father's abusive behaviour.

[25], observed that monsters are "ubiquitous... they are all around us... sometimes, even, they are us" (xxvii). This perspective is evident in the contrasting reactions of Korede and Ayoola to their father's violence. Korede exhibits courage, standing firm despite her tears, while Ayoola displays fear, clinging to her sister for support. This dynamic is further illustrated when their father threatens Ayoola with a cane after a male visitor comes to their home. Ayoola cringes and cries, but Korede bravely joins her sister, holding her hand in solidarity, indifferent to the potential pun-

ishment. Additionally, it is Korede who confronts their Aunt Taiwo with a cane, driving her away when she attempts to take Ayoola to the chief at their father's behest.

This dichotomy in their responses sheds light on why Ayoola becomes the perpetrator of killings, while Korede assumes the role of the cleaner. Ayoola's pervasive fear leads her to act impulsively. She confides to Korede that she carries their father's knife for protection and used it against Femi because "he was over six feet tall and she must have looked like a doll to him, with her small frame" [12]. Ayoola's upbringing, marked by a father who stood "tall and impassive before" her mother, bringing his girlfriends into their home and assaulting her mother for questioning him, shapes her perception of men. Confronted by a towering man like Femi, Ayoola's instinct is to protect herself, even if her actions appear irrational to others. Her traumatic experiences with her father have conditioned her to view men as threats, leading her to carry a knife and resort to violence during conflicts. Unlike someone without her background, Ayoola's immediate reaction is to stab, accentuating how her father's actions have molded her into a monster.

Notably, Ayoola's victims are exclusively men, specifically her lovers. This pattern suggests a correlation between her father's influence and her choice of victims. Upon her father's death, Ayoola seizes his prized possession, a knife, which later becomes her weapon against men. Symbolically, this knife represents the damaging impression her father left on her: that men are vile and deserving of death. This perception becomes her guiding principle, leading her to live a life where her flawed understanding results in her becoming an outcast, even if unintentionally. To support this [26]. ... the knife becomes a potent symbol of the sister's unconscious desires and repressed emotions. Inherited from their abusive father, the knife embodies the negative influence and trauma inflicted upon them, ultimately transforming into a tool for achieving a distorted sense of catharsis through violence [10].

Korede's monstrosity is more complex; although both sisters are shaped by their father's actions, Korede's darker nature might not have fully emerged without Ayoola's killings. Individuals react differently based on their inherent traits and learned values. Korede is portrayed as brave and composed, often contemplating her actions before executing them. While this doesn't guarantee she wouldn't kill impulsively like Ayoola, her tendency to think things through suggests otherwise. In fact, Ayoola evades consequences largely due to Korede's meticulousness.

Despite her composure, Korede is fundamentally similar to Ayoola. As Tade remarks, although Korede doesn't kill, her capabilities make her more dangerous than Ayoola, as she could commit numerous murders and conceal them flawlessly. Thus, Korede's monstrosity stems primarily from their father's actions, which are the root of her abnormality, and partially from Ayoola, as protecting her sister amplifies Korede's darker side. This raises the question: can Ayoola, herself a victim, be responsible for Korede's monstrosity? Regrettably, this is the dilemma, as one damaged individual can create more victims if unchecked, perpetuating a cycle where none fully grasp the extent of the harm they inflict.

In Woman at Point Zero, both individual actions and societal norms contribute to Firdaus's transformation into a monster. Figures such as her father, uncle, husband, Bayoumi, Sharifa, Ibrahim, and Marzouk play pivotal roles, as do oppressive social rules and regulations. The novel traces Firdaus's life, beginning in a setting where fathers marry multiple wives, and children perish frequently: "I had many brothers and sisters. They were like chicks that multiply in spring, shiver in winter and lose their feathers, and then in summer are stricken with diarrhoea, waste away quickly and one by one creep into a corner and die [18]." In this environment, wife-beating is customary, with Firdaus's father assaulting her mother

routinely. For example, when a male child dies, he eats his meal and then beats Firdaus's mother. From an early age, Firdaus passively learns brutality through her father's actions. Her transformation into a figure of monstrosity is intricately linked to the compounded abuses inflicted upon her by both individuals and the patriarchal society at large. From an early age, Firdaus is subjected to a series of traumas that shape her perception of self and the world around her.

Her father embodies the oppressive patriarchal norms, treating his wives and children with blatant disregard. Firdaus recounts the ephemeral nature of her siblings' lives, likening them to "chicks that multiply in spring, shiver in winter and lose their feathers, and then in summer are stricken with diarrhoea, waste away quickly and one by one creep into a corner and die [18]." This metaphor draws attention to the neglect and harsh conditions they endured. Moreover, her father's routine of consuming the family's limited food supply while his children starved exemplifies his callousness.

The sexual abuse by her uncle further entrenches her mistrust and fear of male figures. Despite her academic aspirations, Firdaus faces systemic barriers; her desire for higher education is dismissed with the assertion that such institutions are exclusively for men. Thus, Firdaus said, "I will go to El Azhar and study like you. Then he would laugh and explain that El Azhar was only for men. I would cry, and hold on to his hand..."[16]. Although she (Firdaus) manages to attend secondary school, she is met with emotional neglect, receiving no familial support during significant milestones. She confides in her friend Wafeya, saying, "I am living without love" [26], highlighting her deep sense of isolation [26].

Her subsequent marriage to a much older man introduces her to further physical and emotional abuse. Her husband's invasive scrutiny over trivial matters, such as the amount of food she consumes, and his violent outbursts drive her to seek refuge with her uncle. However, she is met with apathy and justification of her suffering. Her uncle's wife tells her that "it was precisely men well versed in their religion who beat their wives. The precepts of religion permitted such punishment. A virtuous woman was not supposed to complain about her husband. Her duty was perfect obedience [44]." This response reflects the societal normalization of domestic violence under the guise of religious doctrine.

Fleeing her husband's brutality, Firdaus encounters Bayoumi, who initially appears compassionate but soon reveals his exploitative nature by imprisoning and prostituting her. Her ordeal continues under Sharifa, a female pimp who manipulates Firdaus into sex work, further entrenching her in a cycle of exploitation. These experiences culminate in Firdaus's realization of her commodified existence, leading her to assert control by setting her own terms in prostitution. However, this assertion is a double-edged sword, as it both empowers and isolates her, reinforcing her alienation from a society that perpetually dehumanizes her.

Firdaus's trajectory from victim to perceived monster is a testament to the destructive power of systemic patriarchal oppression. Her monstrosity is not innate but a constructed response to relentless subjugation, illustrating how societal and individual actions can deform the human spirit. This shows in Firdaus statement to the narrator, she said:

Let me speak. Do not interrupt me. I have no time to listen to you. They are coming to take me at six o'clock this evening. Tomorrow morning I shall no longer be here. Nor will I be in any place known to man. This journey to a place unknown to everybody on this earth fills me with pride. All my life I have been searching for something that would fill me with pride. Makes me feel superior to everyone else, including kings, princes and rulers [11]. Firdaus's journey is marked by a series of harrowing experiences that shape her perception of self and society. Her initial attempt to reclaim re-

spectability by abandoning prostitution for a secretarial position leads to further disillusionment. Despite relinquishing her material comforts, she finds that women in this "respectable" sphere are similarly objectified, often resorting to compromising their integrity for professional favours. She observes that virtue among the impoverished is not esteemed but rather scorned as naivety, more contemptible than vice: "like the virtue of all those who are poor could never be considered a quality, or an asset, but rather was looked upon as a kind of stupidity, or simple-mindedness to be despised even more than depravity or vice" [94]. Her vulnerability is further exploited when her romantic involvement with a colleague, Ibrahim, ends in betrayal as he chooses to marry the chairman's daughter, leaving Firdaus emotionally shattered.

Disillusioned, Firdaus returns to prostitution, this time achieving a level of autonomy and affluence. She employs top-tier stylists and gains public recognition through charitable acts, understanding that societal honour is often tied to wealth, even if amassed through dishonourable means. She reflects that the last remnants of sanctity within her have been extinguished: "the last drop of sanctity in her blood has finally been shed" [94]. Her final act of defiance occurs when Marzouk, a controlling pimp, attempts to dominate her. Subjected to threats and violence, Firdaus reaches a breaking point and kills Marzouk in self-defense. This act signifies her ultimate rejection of victimhood and a confrontation with her latent rage towards male oppressors. She acknowledges that fear had previously restrained her, but in that decisive moment, she recognizes the fear in her oppressor's eyes, empowering her to act: "why was it that I had never stabbed a man before? I realized that I had been afraid and that the fear had been within me all the time, until the fleeting moment when I read fear in his eyes" [95]. This act becomes her monstrous awakening, a culmination of her resistance against systemic subjugation.

Firdaus's transformation into what society deems monstrous is a direct response to the compounded abuses inflicted upon her by individuals and the patriarchal structures that enable such violations. Her society's rigid gender roles and systemic misogyny curtail her educational aspirations and personal autonomy, leading to a life marked by exploitation and violence. The societal acceptance of domestic abuse, as evidenced by her aunt's admonition that a virtuous woman must endure her husband's beatings without complaint, further entrenches her subjugation: "a virtuous woman was not supposed to complain about her husband. Her duty was perfect obedience" [45].

Firdaus's narrative exemplifies Julia Kristeva's theory of abjection, where the abject is that which disturbs identity, system, and order, existing in a liminal space between subject and object. Kristeva asserts that the abject is "what disturbs identity, system, and order. What does not respect borders, positions, rules. The in-between, the ambiguous, the composite." Firdaus embodies this abjection, as her existence challenges societal norms and exposes the fragility of constructed boundaries between purity and impurity, virtue and vice. Her ultimate act of violence against Marzouk can be seen as a manifestation of this abjection, a rejection of the societal constraints that have sought to define and confine her. Firdaus's descent into perceived monstrosity is a reaction to the relentless oppression and dehumanization she endures. Her story emphasizes the great impact of societal structures on individual identity and the lengths to which one might go to reclaim autonomy and self-worth in the face of systemic injustice.

From the above discussion, it became crystal clear that in the novels, *Woman at Point Zero* and *My Sister the Serial killer*, the women's actions are framed as monstrous by societal standards, yet they are merely reactions to years of violence. Their monstrosity is not an innate trait but a survival mechanism. The novels illustrate how society not only enables but perpetuates female monstrosity. In *My Sister, the Serial Killer*, Korede, though not a murderer herself, becomes complicit in Ayoola's crimes by

helping her cover them up. This reflects how individuals can be shaped by their environments into enablers of monstrosity. Similarly, in *Woman at Point Zero*, Firdaus's descent into prostitution and, ultimately, murder is a result of a patriarchal system that continuously dehumanizes women. When she turns to her uncle for help after fleeing her abusive marriage, his wife tells her: "A virtuous woman was not supposed to complain about her husband. Her duty was perfect obedience" (El Saadawi, 45). This rigid enforcement of gender roles pushes Firdaus further into victimization, ultimately leading her to rebel violently against her oppressors.

Again, both novels depict female monstrosity as a product of trauma, gender oppression, and societal failure. Using Kristeva's Theory of Abjection and Cohen's Monster Culture Theory, this analysis affirms that monstrosity is not an innate condition but a constructed response to violence and marginalization. Ayoola, Korede, and Firdaus are not born monsters; they are made monstrous by the worlds they inhabit. Their stories challenge traditional perceptions of monstrosity, urging readers to consider how societal structures create the very figures they demonize.

Conclusion

Monstrosity has long been a contested concept in literature, with interpretations ranging from supernatural beings to human figures shaped by societal and psychological influences. This study argues that monstrosity is not an inherent trait but a construct shaped by experiences and societal structures. While often perceived as external, monstrosity exists within human society, though frequently overlooked. Examining *My Sister, the Serial Killer* and *Woman at Point Zero* through Kristeva's Theory of Abjection and Cohen's Monster Culture Theory, this study highlights how Ayoola, Korede, and Firdaus embody female monstrosity. Their actions result from trauma and oppression rather than innate evil. Cohen's assertion that "monsters are our children" reinforces that society creates the figures it later fears. Had their environments been different, their monstrous traits may never have emerged. This analysis also questions whether societal laws, meant to regulate behavior, inadvertently create monstrosity by marginalizing individuals. While complete awareness of every action may be unrealistic, fostering greater empathy and inclusivity could reduce the conditions that lead to monstrosity.

Finally, this study challenges traditional notions of villainy, encouraging readers to reconsider moral binaries. However, it also highlights the need for more African scholars to explore monstrosity within African literature. Expanding this discourse would ensure a richer, more contextual understanding of the theme in African narratives.

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